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Problems Embedded in the Indian Commodity Market

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Introduction: Commodity trading has been a topic of controversies since a long time. However, it is marked that commodity trading in India started in an organized form in the nineteenth century with the establishment of the Bombay Cotton Association Limited in the year 1875. When we talk about commodity trading, it is also noticeable that the origin of commodity derivatives market in India backs to thousands of years ago. This existence has been referred to in the Kautilya's Arthashastra. The commodity trading in India has never been regular. It was almost banned for fifty years for a variety of reasons. The commodity trading has, however, regressed in the Indian economy. Now the importance of commodity trading has come into focus. India, being an agriculture based economy, has a good ranking in the production of most of the commodities. More than fifty per cent of the labour force in the country is employed by the agricultural sector which is an important factor in achieving the GDP growth rate target. Hence, it has become more important to promote India in commodity trading.

Discussing the commodity trading, calls for the conceptualization of futures contract. A Futures contract is a standardized contract to buy or sell a specified commodity of a standardized quality in a certain date in future, at a market determined price which is known as the future price. The price is determined by the equilibrium between the forces of supply and demand among competing buy and sells orders at the exchange at the time of the purchase or sale of the contract. Another related term in the commodity trading is the options contract. An option contract gives the option holder the right, but not obligation, to purchase or sell a specific quantity of a commodity at a specific price on or before a specified date. However, both these terms come under a major head known as derivatives which means a financial contract whose value depends upon (or is derived from) the price of another asset. The use of derivatives helps the person to reduce or eliminate risks which may arise in the future. Trading in futures and options not only help in hedging the risk but also gives an opportunity for investment to the speculators who are ready to bear risk in order to get some more return.

Commodity Trading: A Brief History

The forward trading market was never as efficacious as it was seen during the last decade.

There were major downward slopes in the 1960s and 1970s and the time even experienced that the market was inactive. In the 1960s, the commodity derivative markets got a serious setback following the unadorned draughts as the forward contracts could not be fulfilled and hence the government decided negatively and finally banned forward trading. It was much later that in 1970s and 1980s the forward trading rules for some commodities were relaxed by the Government. In the seventies, many of the registered associations became inactive, due to the reason that both futures as well as forward trading in the commodities for which they were registered came to be either postponed or prohibited altogether. The Khusro Committee (June 1980) recommended reintroduction of futures trading in most of the major commodities, including cotton, raw jute, kapas and jute goods. It also suggested that steps may be taken for introducing futures trading in commodities, like potatoes, onions, etc. at an appropriate time. Accordingly futures trading in Potato were initiated during the latter half of 1980 in few markets in Punjab and Uttar Pradesh.

After the introduction of the economic reforms in June 1991 and the subsequent steady trade and industry liberalization in both domestic as well as external sectors, the Government of India in June 1993 appointed one more committee on Forward Markets under Chairmanship of Prof. K.N. Kabra. The Committee submitted its report in September 1994 and the government accepted the recommendations of the committee. Thereafter, the futures trading in a number of commodities were permitted. The liberalized policy followed by the Government of India along with the gradual withdrawal of the procurement and distribution channel demanded for setting in place a market mechanism to perform the economic functions of price discovery and risk management. The National Agriculture Policy announced in July 2000 and the pronouncements of the Hon'ble Finance Minister in the Budget Speech for 2002-2003 were indicative of the Government's resolution to start a mechanism for futures market. Finally, the Government issued notifications permitting the futures trading in the commodities in the year 2003. With the issue of these notifications, futures trading were not prohibited in any commodity. Futures trading then

can be conducted in any commodity subject to the approval of the Government of India. 109 commodities are in the regulated list, i.e. these commodities have been notified under Section 15 of the Forward Contracts (Regulation) Act.

India is among the top 5 producers of most of the commodities in addition to being a major consumer of bullion and energy products. Agriculture contributes 22% to the GDP of the Indian economy. It employs around 57% of the labour force on a total of 163 million hectares of land. This shows that India is a huge market for trading the commodities. The farmer produces various types of crops and the existing socio-economic and political framework makes it difficult for him to change the form of his produce through value-addition / processing and also to make his produce available in another location where the prices may be better. The farmer is well aware of the fact that the immediate post-harvest prices are low it will rise in three to four months. But he cannot wait to take advantage of this price rise. At the same time there are traders and consumers who need the farmers produce in other locations at a specified time in the future. The futures market here helps in matching the offers to sell with the bids to purchase with an objective to avoid costs of transport and storage. It enables the farmers to choose the price at which they want to sell their produce. So it facilitates price discovery and risk-cover with greater certainty. There is a chance that the futures trading can be misused, but to a very limited extent under the present regime in the Indian futures market, which provides for physical delivery in most cases. In a day to day life, price of the commodities fluctuate and the risk of adverse price change creates a threat to businesses. Future trading helps to hedge risk and reduce the risk caused due to unforeseen price changes. Future trading also helps the farmers in deciding which crops to grow.

However, every commodity is not suitable for futures trading. There are some basic requirements to be fulfilled for a commodity to be suitable for future trading for example; the commodity should be capable of standardization and must be storable, the prices must be volatile, and there should not be any government regulations on it.

Commodity Trading Reforms in India

Since the futures trading have the risk of being misused by the unprincipled elements, various regulatory measures have been prescribed by the Forward Markets Commission. The FMC has the power to prohibit a commodity to be traded for a while if the upswing and downswing in the price movement is harmful for the stability of the market. It may sometimes prescribe the minimum and

maximum limits for the futures price for stabilizing the prices in future and thus save the market from the ill effects of crisis. When we consider the importance of agriculture in India's GDP and the genuine requirements of promoting sound commodity futures markets in the country, a number of major reforms have been undertaken since the early 1990s.

These include the setting up of a separate Department of Consumer Affairs in the year 1995 which has been leading the major initiatives in reviving the commodity futures trading in India. The major efforts at reforming and strengthening the Commodity Exchanges were made in the year 1996 which included the broad basing the Board, computerization, professionalization and online trading are at different stages of implementation in various exchanges. The introduction of futures trading in edible oils, oilseeds and their cakes in the year 1998 was a major landmark in the development of commodity futures contracts in India. There was an introduction of a major reform package for FMC and the Exchanges by means of a World Bank-funded IDF Grant in 1998 for removing the prohibition on all minor oilseed, oil and cake. Moving forward, there have been various other reforms that helped promote the trading in commodities. These included the lifting up of the ban over the interstate movement of the agricultural products, more and more commodities have been notified by FMC to avoid fluctuations in prices etc. Several electronic trading exchanges known as National Multi-Commodity Exchanges (NMCE) have been set up since 2002. The two such important commodity exchanges are: Multi-Commodity Exchange of India Ltd. (MCX) and National Multi-Commodity & Derivatives Exchange of India Limited (NCDEX).

Problems and Suggestions

Although the commodity derivatives market has made great development in the last few years, the real issues facing the future of the market have not yet been resolved. It is remarkable that the total number of future commodities and value and volume of the future commodities has increased but there have been several problems that still need to be dealt with. The objectives of setting up of the commodity derivative exchanges have not been achieved till date and the growth rates witnessed is not expected to be sustainable unless the real issues are sorted out as soon as possible. The major problems of the Indian Commodity Market can be discussed as below:

1. Commodity options:

The first and foremost problem of the Indian Commodity Market is the absence of options trading. The futures market makes a farmer to hedge

commodities. The report of the Abhijit Sen Committee reveal that a notification was issued to curb out this problem stating that all the commodities with similar risk profile would follow an uniform norm while the margins would be set at the exchange level because different exchange have different risk factors with regards to clearing houses and margin being a function of clearing house risk is highly affected.

11. Irregular Gaps in Trading of various Commodities:

As stated earlier, the Government started banning the commodity trading in the year 1952. Cash settlement and option trading was banned in 1952 and the derivatives trading was shifted to informal forwards market. Commodity derivatives were banned completely in the late '60s, but were revived again in the '80s. After the successful equity market reforms of the '90s, the Government of India tried to repeat similar reforms for the commodity derivatives markets and in 1999 suggested that the Minimum Support Price (MSP) as a price-hedging instrument could be replaced with derivatives markets. National-level multi-commodity exchanges were permitted to be set up on conditions of being backed by internationally prevailing best practices of trading, clearing and settlement. But the Government was found influencing the commodity trading through imposing bans in the trading of certain commodities from time to time. In January 2007, the Government banned futures trading in wheat, rice, tur and urad in an attempt to control inflation. These commodities contributed 6.65 per cent in the country's total agriculture, and thus the Abhijit Sen Committee concluded that although it has affected the market mechanism but the futures trading was not much affected. On 7 May, 2008, the Indian Government announced the ban on futures trading in four commodities from the agri-commodity group, viz; chickpea, potato, rubber and soy oil. The attempt to control prices forces the

government to impose these bans, but there stands no logic for this. These irregularities have added to declining growth of the commodity trading.

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